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The kinetochore is a target for therapeutic intervention in human cancer: the outer plate.

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We hypothesized that inhibition of kinetochore components would be associated with a specifically high therapeutic index, indicating an intrinsic bias towards kinetochore inhibition in cancer. We studied here total transcription following genetic deletion of two major kinetochore components, Spc25 and CENP-E.